

Development of New Copper and Iron Reflected Critical Benchmarks Using Reference Core Composed in LR-0 Reactor

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ABSTRACT

The reference core composed in the LR-0 reactor is a simple reactor arrangement composed of six fuel assemblies. Due to good knowledge of its geometry and the suitable properties of the used fuel assemblies, a benchmark reference neutron field in the core center was identified. It is one of 13 basic reference fields worldwide. Currently, the core is used in an integral approach, where the core influence region, namely the center or the reflector region, is an object whose neutronic properties are studied. For such purposes, the benchmark model was improved, and as many geometrical and material parameters as possible were reevaluated. Fuel dimensions were remeasured, fuel composition was characterized by SIMS, cladding composition by mass spectrometry, and activation analysis. This new benchmark model was used for the characterization of new critical experiments with iron and copper in various positions in the core. The reference model, having a void center and being reflected by water, is underpredicting by about 100pcm when using ENDF/B-VIII.1 data library. It is worth noting that for both iron and copper, it is reported improvement of neutronic properties when simulated in ENDF/B-VIII.1 instead of ENDF/B-VIII.0. However, some discrepancies persist, namely in the case where the iron block is located in the core center, when notable underprediction is reported. Generally, the presented results are suitable for the validation of the iron and copper cross section within its effect on criticality.

Keywords: LR-0 reactor; Iron reflected core, Copper neutron reflector

1. INTRODUCTION

Both iron and copper are important reactor structural component materials. Due to that fact, their cross sections had been reevaluated in the new ENDF/B-VIII.1 nuclear data library. A large set of experiments using copper and iron [1] has been realized at the mentioned fast neutron assemblies, and the improvement of k_{eff} when a new evaluation is released confirms improvement in the fast neutron energy region. For reliable comparisons, well characterized critical assembly is needed. This work aims to compare the influence of the structural material on the reactivity in the core for different libraries.

The current paper deals with the development of a new, improved benchmark model of the LR-0 reference core, in which the benchmark reference neutron field was identified. The old version of the benchmark used tabulated parameters, which in the new benchmark were reevaluated using a new analysis using dummy elements (cladding pins, dummy pellet, and dummy spacing grid). The large development in XRF analysis allows non-destructively analysis of the core components. Using SIMS and AMS analysis of dummy fuel pellets, the level of fuel impurities and ^{234}U was determined. The analysis of dummy cladding rod allows the determination of the precise content of Hf and Nb in cladding rods as well as the density of the raw material. In older benchmarks, these effects, especially the effect of ^{234}U , are evaluated as bias, while in the new one, it is part of the benchmark model. The k_{eff} of the new and old models are nearly the same, but this new approach allows to decrease the related uncertainties.

It is worth noting that the biases, mostly the effect of ^{234}U , do not matter when the core is primarily used as the neutron source in reactor dosimetry experiments focused on the measurement of spectrum

averaged cross sections. In such experiments, the dominating uncertainty is in the total neutron flux (i.e., scaling factor) used for normalization of dosimeters, being about 2 – 3 %. The bias in neglectation of ^{234}U is not more than 200 pcm, thus it is negligible in reaction rate evaluations.

2. REACTOR ARRANGEMENT

LR-0 is a pool type, zero power reactor moderated by light water. The core is placed inside a cylindrical aluminum tank, which is in massive concrete shielding (*Figure 1*). The fuel, which is used for core composition, has in radial profile an identical geometry with VVER-1000 fuel; its length is shortened to 125 cm. The core is assembled on a special plate, which enables forming of nearly arbitrary arrangements, including changing the lattice pitch. The bottom of the tank is in a special radiation shielding bunker, where the VVER-1000 neutron transport Mock-Up is assembled. This is another involvement of LR-0 in the reactor dosimetry experimental program. Part of the VVER-1000 Mock-Up, namely the simulator of the VVER-1000 reactor internals, is placed near the vessel wall on the benchmark plate. They are present during all experiments, as they are massive and heavy stainless steel structures and have a negligible effect on criticality.

Figure 1. Scheme of special core assembled in LR-0 reactor.

2.1. Experimental Arrangement

The experiments were carried out at a reference core configuration consisting of six fuel assemblies with a nominal enrichment of 3.3 wt.% surrounding a central dry assembly. A benchmark reference neutron field was identified within this central assembly and is one of 13 basic reference fields in the IRDFF-II database [2]. Due to its extremely well-defined geometry, this configuration can be used as a reference case.

Between 2023 and 2025, a series of reactor physics experiments were carried out to study the effect of iron, in the form of low-alloy steel, on criticality. In 2024, the experimental campaign continued with measurements focusing on the effect of a copper cylinder on system criticality.

Figure 2. Scheme of benchmarked configurations.

2.2. Measurement of critical water level

Reactivity of the cores for the described experiments is driven exclusively by the moderator level. In such case, the moderator level (H_{cr}) acts as a critical parameter. If the moderator level slightly exceeds the H_{cr} , the one-group asymptotic approximation may be used to express the reactivity (1):

$$\rho(H) = \frac{C}{(H_{cr} + \lambda_z)^2} \left[\frac{1}{\left(1 + \frac{H - H_{cr}}{H_{cr} + \lambda_z}\right)^2} - 1 \right]; \rho = \frac{k_{eff} - 1}{k_{eff}}; k_{eff} = \frac{k_{\infty}}{1 + M^2 B^2} \quad (1)$$

where C is constant; $C = \frac{M^2 \pi^2}{k_{\infty}}$; B^2 geometry buckling, M^2 migration area and λ_z is the axial extrapolation length.

For low reactivities, the formula (1) may be expanded into the Taylor series around the H_{cr} as described by expression (2):

$$\rho(H) = f(H, a_1, a_2) = a_1 \cdot (H - a_2) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{3}{2} \frac{H - a_2}{a_2 + \lambda_z} \right) \quad (2)$$

where $a_1 = \frac{\delta \rho}{\delta H}$; $a_2 = H_{cr}$

Using this formula, critical levels and reactivity coefficients were evaluated from different supercritical states measured using the inverse kinetics method based on the time-dependent response of counters placed in the instrumentation tubes around the reactor core. The total uncertainty of the H_{cr} evaluation is 0.058 cm and includes the technical tolerance and the uncertainty of the level meter calibration.

2.3. Calculations

The calculations were performed with the MCNP6 code [4] and various nuclear data libraries: ENDF/B-VIII [5] and the previous evaluation ENDF/B-VIII [6]. Calculations have been performed in the critical mode of the MCNP6.2 code using 10000 generations and 40000 neutrons in one generation

The improved reactor calculational model was compiled using as many experimental parameters as possible. The composition of the structural components was identified by XRF, and a tabulated density value of 7.9 g/cm^3 was used. The fuel and cladding composition were characterized using destructive analysis using a dummy pellet and a dummy cladding rod. The geometrical parameters were characterized by direct measurements.

In the calculations, the experimental value was used for the critical water level.

2.3.1. New geometrical approach

The most influential parameter, fuel pin diameter, was precisely measured. 90 randomly selected pins from the core were measured at 7 levels in their flooded part. The new value of $9.139 \text{ mm} \pm 0.013 \text{ mm}$ is consistent with the previous value of $9.150 \text{ mm} \pm 0.016 \text{ mm}$ and also corresponds with the producer data of 9.1 mm with a tolerance of $9.05 \text{ mm} - 9.18 \text{ mm}$.

Primary improvement of the new model is that it does not contain homogenizations. In the previous approach, the fuel assembly socket, fuel pin bottom cap, and spacing grid were homogenized with the moderator. In the new approach, all components were simulated without homogenization. The drawings of these parts are not available, so the lower part of the pin was divided into five parts, ranging from 0.6 cm to 3 cm in height, which were characterized by directly determined volume and outer surface. The central part is assumed to be a cylinder. This means that the only simplification is that the element's thickness is assumed to be homogeneous along the axial segment. Their volumes were determined by weighting in water.

The spacing grids also have a great influence, as they are located in the maximum neutron flux. The special shape of the element was simulated as the ring touching the boundary of the hexagonal fuel pins grid. Geometry is conserving the mass of the grid element. The masses of special parts (frame and central pin holder) were characterized from the dummy grid by dismantling it. The validity of this approach was confirmed by calculation. The criticality was calculated when the spacer grid element is placed in the half thickness of the water moderator or directly touching the fuel pin *Figure 4*. The differences between cases with various gaps between fuel pins and spacer grid elements simulated as ring are not higher than 17 pcm. Taking into account the fact, that uncertainty in exact position is not more than 1/10 of gap, the effect of mispositioning of spacing element can be neglected.

It is worth noting that using a heterogeneous approach instead of a homogeneous one for the grid introduces a k_{eff} change of about ~ 100 pcm.

Figure 3. View on the bottom part fuel assembly inserted in socket and view on model

Figure 4. Calculational model with modified position of spacer grid elements, calculations in ENDF/B-VIII.0 with uncertainty 0.00005.

2.3.2. Evaluation of structural components materials

The highest flux from structural components is in the cladding, thus the exact composition of the cladding alloy is needed. In the past, producer data was used in the model, while in the new model, experimental values obtained by mass spectrometry were used. The dummy pin from the same batch of pins was analyzed using X-ray fluorescence (XRF), mass spectrometry and neutron activation analysis (NAA) using LVR-15 irradiation reactor in Rez. Its worth noting, the XRF cannot analyze the Hf amount in sample, while both mass spectrometry and activation analysis are on good agreement between both. It level is very important, because it is strong neutron absorber.

Molybdenum detected by XRF was not confirmed by both mass spectrometry and NAA. In case of niobium XRF highly overpredicts both NAA and mass spectrometry. Even more the NAA was able to determine the tantalum in concentration 2 ppm. Tantalum accompanied niobium, and in this case tantalum concentration in niobium is 130 ppm. This value is considerably smaller than often reported 700 ppm in classical niobium foils. The density was also determined experimentally being 6.55 g/cm³ instead of tabulated being 6.44 g/cm³.

Table I. Composition of fuel cladding additives.

	Mass spectrometry		NAA in LRV-15 reactor		XRF analysis		Tabulated composition	
	Mean [wt. %]	Unc. [wt. %]	Mean [wt. %]	Unc. [wt. %]	Mean [wt. %]	Unc. [wt. %]	Mean [wt. %]	Unc. [wt. %]
Hf	0.040	0.0032	0.045	0.0046	-	-	0.03	-
Mo	-	-	-	-	0.80	0.19	-	-
Nb	1.10	0.09	1.25	0.18	1.64	0.09	1.0	-
Zr	97.7	7.8	-	-	97.56	0.52	98.97	-

2.3.3. Evaluation of fuel materials

Compared to the previous benchmark model, the newly developed model accounts for the effect of ²³⁴U in k_{eff} to be about 200 pcm. In the previous model, it was evaluated as a bias using ²³⁴U data available from similar reactors, because the producer data is not available. In the new model, the ²³⁴U level was determined by approximation between experimental values for the same producer fuel determined by means of SIMS analysis *Figure 5*. The fuel contamination was determined by AMS, and the obtained

data are below the limits defined by the producer. Boron is approximately 80 % of the limit value, manganese is approximately 25 % and other contaminants are less than 5 % of the limit.

It is worth noting that the producer declares that the fuel for research reactors is not produced from irradiated materials, but SIMS analysis confirms the presence of ^{236}U in the studied material. This fact confirms the validity of the independent confirmation of the data presented in the datasheet. However, the effect of ^{236}U was neglected, as the observed level is approximately twice lower than ^{234}U , and ^{236}U capture is more than 20 times smaller.

Figure 5. Concentration of ^{234}U depending on fuel enrichment.

2.4. Measured critical parameter

The critical water levels were evaluated from a series of repeated experimental results. The means are presented in *Table II*. The reference case (A) with a void channel has the smallest critical water level, which can be understood as confirmation of excellent water reflecting properties. In the other two cases (D, E), the reflector is formed by 12 steel cylinders. When the iron cylinder is placed into the core center, the critical water level increases. This increase reflects the fact that in this geometry, iron (low alloy steel) acts as an absorber rather than a reflector. When the central cavity is filled with copper instead of iron (C), the critical water level is even higher than in all cases with iron. This is the reflection of higher neutron absorption in copper than in iron.

Table II. Evaluated experimental water levels.

Case	Material in central module	Material at core boundary	H_{cr} [cm]	Total standard Uncertainty [cm]
A	Empty	-	54.23	0.12
B	Fe	-	57.82	0.07
C	Cu	.	61.04	0.05
D	Empty	12 * Fe	55.57	0.07
E	Fe	12 * Fe	59.71	0.10

2.5. Effect of gap between fuel assemblies

The most notable source of uncertainty was identified being the gap between fuel assemblies. The lattice pitch is 23.6 cm, and the outer dimension of the fuel is 23.4 cm. By engineering judgment, the uncertainty in the gap was estimated to be 1 mm in the upper edge. The critical water level (the flooded part of the fuel assembly) is not more than 62.5 cm, which is half the length of the assembly; thus, the uncertainty in gap thickness is estimated to be 0.5 mm. The uncertainty was evaluated by calculation. To precisely evaluate this effect, a set of H_{cr} with different thick gap between assemblies was carried out in *Table III*. Taking into account the water level reactivity coefficient being ~ 260 pcm/cm, the reactivity introduced by a 1 mm shift in gap thickness is about 110 pcm. This value is consistent, but slightly smaller than the calculational prediction, being ~ 150 pcm.

Table III. Evaluated water level in reference case and increased gap between assemblies

Gap [mm]	H_{cr} [mm]	Unc. [mm]
0	542.3	0.11
1	538.1	0.24
3	531.1	0.20
5	527.3	0.04

3. RESULTS

The precise calculational model was used for simulations of k_{ef} for various arrangements using the reference core. The experimental water levels were used in the compilation of the mathematical model (see *Table II*). The calculated results are presented in *Table IV*. As the simulated arrangements are critical the experimental value is in all cases 1, and the discrepancy is the difference from this value. It is worth noting that both ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 slightly underpredict the experiment. In the reference case (A) and the case with the iron lateral reflector (D), the discrepancy is not higher than the uncertainty. In cases when the iron or copper block is in the center of the core, the rate of underprediction is significantly higher than in the reference case.

Table IV. Result of calculated k_{eff} using new benchmark model and ENDF/B-VIII.0 and ENDF/B-VIII.1 libraries

	ENDF/B-VIII.0	ENDF/B-VIII.1	ENDF/B-VIII.1*	Uncertainty
Case A	0.99873	0.99907	1.00072	0.00097
Case B	0.99659	0.99685	0.99844	0.00082
Case C	0.99603	0.99619	0.99787	0.00083
Case D	0.99897	0.99947	1.00097	0.00132
Case E	0.99454	0.99545	0.99680	0.00120

*The oxygen evaluation from INDEN was used in combination with ENDF/B-VIII.1

4. CONCLUSIONS

The critical experiments with iron and copper blocks were realized using the benchmark reference neutron field at the LR-0 reactor in Rež. The new evaluation of ENDF/B-VIII.1 shows better agreement than the previous ENDF/B-VIII.0. When the core is reflected by iron cylinders, notable improvement is reported. When the iron is in the core center, improvement is reported, but still discrepancy is persisting. In case of copper in central assembly, notable underprediction is reported as well.

The new heterogenous benchmark model provides results closer to real observations, and additionally uncertainty interval could be decreased due to precise description of previously simplified regions. Its

was also demonstrated that the precise characterization of used nuclear materials, especially fuel and cladding, is essential for obtaining best estimate uncertainties.

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